

THE ROLE OF LESSON PLANNING TO IMPROVE FUTURE TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to determining the categories of professional knowledge that pre-service English teachers use while creating a lesson plan. The qualitative research approach was used in this study. The findings imply that when participants construct a lesson plan; they use a variety of professional expertise. These include subject knowledge, general pedagogical knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge, curricular knowledge, learned knowledge, and educational context knowledge. It is advised that EFL pre-service education encourages prospective teachers to reflect on their teaching practices so that they can remodel their professional knowledge associated with successful teaching practices progressively and permanently.

Introduction. Pedagogical factors, such as foreign language instructors' lesson preparation procedures, may affect students' low English performance in the national context. Teachers express the components of instructional processes, such as learning objectives, material, resources, assessment, and classroom relationships, via lesson preparation (Riddell, 2014). Lesson plans in the ELT environment show instructors' methodological orientations on how to teach a language, which shapes their decisions and classroom activities (Chaves & Hernández, 2012).

Main part. Pedagogical content knowledge can be related to both traditional and constructivist techniques in the context of English language acquisition.

In classical techniques, learning is defined as the relationship between particular environmental stimuli and people's responses or suitable reactions to them (Ertmer & Newby, 2013). Foreign language learning, in this sense, involves habit building. This would be the result of consistent practice with linguistic topics like grammar and vocabulary (Hall, 2011; Richards & Rodgers, 2014). Constructivist methods, on the other hand, highlight that learning involves meaning creation processes (Coll, 1990; Soler, 2006).

In the context of lesson preparation, pedagogical content knowledge may also be associated with the selection or development of learning objectives, topics, activities, materials, and assessments. Learning objectives are goals that specify

the outcomes that students must attain at the end of academic activity. Learning objectives in the context of foreign or second language instruction are connected to the development of communicative skills.

Content is connected to the knowledge that students build and is classified in to four types: factual, conceptual, procedural, and attitudinal content. The former relates to literal information such as statistics, facts, or terminology that are often memorized. The preceding aspects are included in conceptual material, but their comprehension is considered.

Building a plan is a creative and vital process in which instructors use a variety of tactics to engage students, measure progress, and encourage learning and understanding, all while keeping the kids on the receiving end in mind. It is a period when instructors see all of the jigsaw pieces and assess how they will fit together to create a successful learning experience.

Lesson planning allows instructors to enter the classroom each day fully prepared to teach new ideas and conduct meaningful conversations rather than puzzling things out as they go. Students might easily lose concentration in the absence of a lesson plan, and teachers may find themselves grasping for ideas on what to do next.

Professional development for teachers may or may not be required. Some professional development may be regarded as mandatory because the skills and knowledge that the development activities attempt to improve are thought to be crucial for teacher quality. Participation in such events may even be compulsory for

teacher certification in some circumstances. It is also crucial for teachers to use their professional judgment when picking and participating in development activities that they believe would be most useful to them. A high level of mandatory professional development may indicate a more tightly supervised professional development system with less flexibility for instructors to pick the development they believe they require.

On average among the participating countries, some 51% of teachers' professional development was compulsory (Table 3.1). The proportion ranged from about one-third or less in Austria, Belgium (Fl.), Denmark and Portugal to 78% in Malta and as high as 88% in Malaysia. The countries with the highest number of compulsory days on average were Mexico, Bulgaria, Spain, Italy and Korea and those with the lowest were Austria, Belgium (Fl.) and Ireland.

Conclusion. When designing classes, pre-service EFL instructors examine many forms of knowledge, including subject knowledge, general pedagogical knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge, curricular knowledge, learner knowledge, and understanding of educational environments. These are necessary for the lesson planning process. It is proposed that pre-service EFL teacher training programs support the restructuring of teacher professional knowledge from a conventional to a communicative approach of language teaching and learning. This should be accomplished by encouraging future teachers to reflect on their practices to alter the professional teacher knowledge that informs them.

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